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The Intersection of Mental Health, Marginalisation and Media: A Critical Analysis of Jeffrey Dahmer's Path to Criminality

M B Aswathy

Department of English,
Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham,
Amritapuri, India.

Indu A S

Department of English,
Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham,
Amritapuri, India.

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Abstract:

This paper analyses the Netflix series *Monster: The Jeffrey Dahmer Story* (2022) to explore media sensationalism and systemic failures that influenced the portrayal of Jeffrey Dahmer and contributed to his prolonged criminality. It investigates whether the series merely sensationalizes Dahmer's crime as a symbol of fear and morbid fascination for the shock value or presents him as a complex figure shaped by institutional negligence and missed opportunities, which ultimately reduced him down to the label of "Monster" By applying socio-psychological frameworks such as social disorganization theory, strain theory and labelling theory, this paper aims to provide a deeper understanding of the systemic breakdowns within society and its institutions that enabled his path to criminality to continue over a decade. The depiction of Jeffrey Dahmer serves as a critical entry point into broader discussions on mental illness, systemic failures and the ethics of the true-crime representation in media.

Keywords: Jeffrey Dahmer, Media sensationalism, Mental health, Police negligence, Socio-psychological theories, Systemic negligence.

"17 Killed, and a Life Is Searched for Clues" (The New York Times, 14 August 1991)

The true crime genre plays a vital role in shaping the public perceptions of criminality. However, it often blurs the line between reality and sensationalism, sparking controversy over how the media portrays these crimes. With the rise of digital platforms, crime narratives have expanded into various forms, ranging from documentaries like "*Burari Deaths*" or "*Curry and Cyanide*" to fictionalized accounts such as "*Mindhunter*". This genre has become so popular that a significant portion of the public considers crime narratives their favourite content.

Documentaries often focus on real-life investigations or mysteries, while fictionalized accounts turn notorious crimes into entertainment, often blurring the line between fact and fiction. Such fictionalized retellings of many major crimes have solidified their status in popular culture and shaped the public's views of both the criminal and legal systems.

The depiction of serial killers has always been a subject of controversy, debate and fascination. Serial killers have emerged as significant figures in the true crime genre, often portrayed by the media as complex antiheroes or even glorified. By transforming actual criminals into pseudo-celebrities and concealing the suffering of victims and their families, this representation has the potential to distort public opinion about the exact nature of the crime.

Jeffrey Lionel Dahmer remains one of the most infamous names in criminal history. His gruesome crimes sent a shockwave of fear and curiosity throughout American society, leading to widespread media coverage of his crime and cementing a monstrous image to his name. Dahmer's crimes have been repeatedly explored through various formats, including courtroom proceedings, real-time news coverage, and the intimate perspectives shared in interviews and fictionalized accounts. Between 1978 and 1991, Dahmer murdered seventeen young men through acts of homicide, necrophilia and cannibalism, targeting individuals from racial minorities or the LGBTQ community. This continuous obsession with his story reflects

the public's deep-rooted fixation on serial killers and the blurred representation of real-life violence as entertainment.

The Netflix series *Monster: The Jeffrey Dahmer Story* (2022) stands out as one of the most recent and controversial retellings of Dahmer's criminality. It garnered widespread attention and critical acclaim for its dramatized yet deeply immersive portrayal of his life and the circumstances that enabled his crimes. The series delves into Dahmer's childhood, sexuality, unusual interests, and compulsive behaviours, while also laying bare the graphic details of his violence. Beyond personal exploration, it underscores the broader societal and institutional failures that allowed his crimes to go undetected for years.

Unlike many past portrayals, the series shifts through multiple narrative perspectives, which not only shed light on Jeffrey Dahmer's life but also highlight the voices of multiple people who were struggling to come to terms with his crime and the brutality of his actions. It further exposes the multiple layers of systemic breakdown within law enforcement, particularly how authorities repeatedly failed to act on a neighbour's complaints about Dahmer's suspicious behaviour or dismissed victims' pleas due to racial and minority biases, highlighting the institutional limitations of 1980s American society. The series also provides an ambiguous portrayal of Dahmer's mental health, exploring his troubled childhood, social isolation, and compulsive, disturbing tendencies without directly linking his crimes to mental illness.

By analyzing Dahmer's case beyond the context of media sensationalism, this paper aims to provide a deeper understanding of how societal structure and systemic failures contributed to his path of criminality by combining the socio-psychological theories such as Social disorganization theory, Strain theory and Labelling theory.

Social disorganization theory proposes that weakened social institutions such as family, education, and law enforcement create an environment conducive to criminal behaviour. Dahmer's early life was marked by parental neglect, isolation, and instability, factors that

contributed to the escalation of his deviant actions. This theory helps explain how his social circumstances may have influenced or reinforced his criminal behaviour.

Strain theory suggests that an individual often turns to deviance when they experience a disconnect between acceptable societal goals and the actual means of achieving them. Dahmer's inability to create meaningful social relationships and his feelings of alienation led him to extreme and aberrant behaviour as a way to fulfil his psychological needs. His crimes can be interpreted as an alternative response to his inability to conform to traditional social norms. This theory offers insight into how societal pressures may drive individuals toward criminal behaviour.

Labelling theory examines how societal reactions or assigned labels can shape an individual's behaviour. Despite early signs of psychological disturbance, Dahmer was frequently dismissed by others as a misfit. Law enforcement's reluctance to take action driven largely by racial and sexual biases enabled him to continue his crimes. This theory highlights how societal labels and reactions can reinforce deviant behaviour. By combining these theories, this paper argues that Dahmer's crimes were not merely an anomaly but a consequence of systemic breakdown, which allowed his deviance to persist and fuelled a cycle of violence that early intervention might have prevented.

This paper aims to move beyond the simplistic dichotomy of "monster or victim" by analyzing Dahmer's crimes through the lens of broader socio-structural conditions, rather than attributing them solely to personal pathology. The Netflix series *Monster: The Jeffrey Dahmer Story* exemplifies how true crime media can reshape public perception by highlighting victim voices and institutional failures instead of focusing solely on the killer's mental state and exaggerated glorification. Drawing on socio-psychological frameworks such as Social Disorganization Theory, Strain Theory, and Labelling Theory, this paper critically examines how Dahmer's actions were shaped by both social and personal factors. Ultimately, Jeffrey Dahmer's case is

not merely a disturbing anomaly, but a tragic reflection of institutional bias, neglected social responsibility, and the media's tendency to sensationalize crime and justice.

1. Systemic failures and Missed warnings

Jeffrey Dahmer's case stands as a chilling example of how deeply rooted systemic failures and overlooked warning signs can culminate in unimaginable tragedy. His decade-long killing spree was not only a sign of a disturbed mind but also a stark critique of the repeated systemic inertia and failure to intervene. Dahmer's victims were mostly young men of colour or individuals who identified as part of the LGBTQ+ community, overlooked by institutions due to racism and homophobia. The disregard for community voices, especially of Black and LGBTQ+ people, highlights the act of bias that enabled Dahmer's actions to continue unnoticed. At the same time, his untreated psychological disorder, unstable personal life and repressed sexuality contribute to his troubled mental state. Collectively, these missed opportunities and systemic blind spots reveal a harsh reality that society often overlooks the marginalized and turns a blind eye to the mental health issues that allow the dangerous individuals to remain undetected.

1.1 Law enforcement

Dahmer killed seventeen young men over more than ten years, many of whom were men of colour and identified as a part of the LGBTQ community. The Jeffrey Dahmer case remains a sobering example of the deep-rooted systemic flaws within both the legal system and law enforcement that allow heinous crimes to continue undetected for long. His ability to remain undetected was not just about manipulation or strategy but also about multiple missed opportunities due to institutional biases and the lack of attention and urgency in protecting marginalized lives.

One of the primary examples of this systemic failure occurred on 27 May, 1991, when the neighbours discovered fourteen-year-old Konerak Sinthasomphone, who managed to

escape from Dahmer's apartment that evening - bruised and obviously in distress. Alarmed neighbours and bystanders sensing the impending danger dialled the police. However, when the officers arrived, they accepted Dahmer's explanation that the boy was his nineteen-year-old boyfriend and that they were simply having an argument. The police returned the boy to Dahmer without verifying his age or identity or discerning any physical injuries, thereby disregarding the pleas and concerns of the bystanders. The very "protectors" handed over the prey to its predator; within hours, the boy was dead.

This moment is not only heartbreaking, but it also highlights the dangerous consequences of racial and sexuality-based bias prevailing within law enforcement. Most of the bystanders who attempted to defend Konerak were Black women, such as Sandra Smith and Nicole Childress, but the police denied their requests. Before this incident, Glenda Cleveland, another neighbour of Dahmer, had already made several calls to the police suspicious of his actions throughout his killing spree. She even provided them with the name of the boy she believed was in danger. However, the authorities shrugged off every one of her desperate efforts to persuade them to act. If the police had taken these complaints seriously, many lives might have been saved. Cleveland's experience with the so-called "lawkeepers" reveals the lack of security and vulnerability faced by minority communities in a society that claims to be governed by strong laws.

There's a clear pattern here: the lives of gay men and men of colour were treated as less worthy of protection, while the voices of women especially Black women were consistently ignored. In the late 1980s and early 1990s, homosexual relationships were often viewed with unease, misunderstanding, or outright hostility, and LGBTQ+ stigma remained widespread. When Dahmer told officers he was involved in a same-sex relationship, it further deterred the officers from investigating the matter. Instead of intervening, the police appeared eager to

distance themselves from what they framed as a “private matter”, an unfair decision based on ignorance and bias.

The legal system, like law enforcement, failed to recognize the severity of Dahmer’s behaviour early on, resulting in missed chances that proved fatal. In 1989, Dahmer was found guilty of sexually abusing Konarak’s older brother. Instead of facing severe penalties, Dahmer received a light sentence of probation and spent only ten months in a work release program. There was no follow-up to monitor his behaviour, and the system treated him as a low-risk offender, ignoring the fact that his actions were part of a much darker pattern. This leniency raises serious questions about how the legal system handles cases involving sexual violence, especially when the victims are men of colour and part of the LGBTQ+ community. Dahmer’s ability to appear cooperative and clean-cut likely influenced the court’s decision. He managed to walk away easily because he did not fit the prescribed stereotype of a predator. The fact that the same man went on to kill the younger brother of his previous victim just two years later shows how critical that misjudgment was.

Over the years, several missing person reports were filed in connection to Dahmer’s victims, yet no significant link was established between them. There was no centralized effort to identify the patterns, primarily due to miscommunication and the siloed nature between the various agencies. If these departments had shared information and worked together, the truth about Dahmer might have surfaced much sooner.

Dahmer’s neighbours had noticed the strange smells, disturbing noises and other warning signs. Despite their repeated complaints, the police took no action. Instead of being regarded as valid concerns, these complaints were dismissed and treated as a nuisance, something not worth listening to or considered an exaggeration.”.

There is much more to Jeffrey Dahmer’s case than just one serial killer’s activities. It reveals the interplay of judicial leniency, police negligence, racial bias, and homophobia as the

root cause of systemic failure Dahmer was able to carry out his crimes for years not because he was careful or smart enough to cover them up, but because he specifically targeted people whom society frequently overlooked. The institutions designed to protect the public repeatedly failed by ignoring the concerns of minority communities, minimizing early crimes and failing to coordinate investigations.

Addressing these failures means confronting the unsettling reality that, historically, not all lives have been treated equally under the law. The 1980s were defined by widespread stigma against both race and sexual orientation. Though recent years have seen some progress, past injustices remain vital reminders that law enforcement and judicial systems must recognize these patterns, listen to marginalized voices, and work toward building institutions that truly serve and protect everyone equally.

1.2 Missed warning: Importance of Mental health

Jeffrey Dahmer's case remains one of the most disturbing and complex in the history of American criminal behaviour. His actions were the result of a combination of untreated mental health conditions, problematic family dynamics and a lack of early psychological intervention. His case effectively illustrates the devastating impact of mental illness combined with emotional instability, unresolved trauma and a confused sense of self.

Dahmer's mental state was far from simple. Throughout his life, he displayed symptoms of multiple mental disorders, including borderline personality disorder (BPD), schizotypal personality disorder (SPD) and paraphilia. Many of Dahmer's traits align with BPD, a disorder marked by emotional instability, fear of abandonment, and impulsivity. His personality and interpersonal dysfunction also reflect SPD, a condition defined by distorted thinking, deviant behaviour, and detachment from reality.

Although the matter is still up for debate, experts have also suggested that he might have displayed traits of Asperger's syndrome, a developmental disorder characterized by

difficulties with communication, social interaction, and repetitive behaviours. Notably, Professor James Fallon, who has studied the brains of psychopaths, argued that Dahmer's actions were more closely aligned with borderline personality disorder than with psychopathy. Fallon highlighted his ability to express remorse and empathy, suggesting that, unlike true psychopaths, he struggled emotionally and was not entirely devoid of human connection or emotions. Dahmer's uncertainty about his sexual orientation added yet another level of complexity to his psychological profile.

Throughout his adolescence and adulthood, Dahmer grappled with intense feelings of loneliness and shame due to his homosexuality. He struggled to find a healthy outlet for his sexuality during a time when such desires were heavily stigmatized. His compulsive tendencies and desire to dominate and control were likely the result of this internal conflict. His inability to form emotionally fulfilling or socially acceptable romantic relationships may have contributed to his disturbing fantasy of creating a submissive "zombie" companion. This fantasy reveals a combination of sexual frustration and emotional isolation.

Dahmer's background further underscores the significance of early emotional development in shaping mental health. He had a very unstable family environment around him. As a result, his mental health was significantly impacted by his parents' frequent arguments, emotional unavailability, and eventual divorce in 1978. His mother, who struggled with her mental health, eventually abandoned the family, leaving Dahmer alone and deeply rejected. This early trauma created an intense feeling of abandonment and alienation, which eventually resulted in his criminal behaviour. His father, Lionel Dahmer, had a particular influence on him, as he introduced young Jeffrey to dissecting dead animals. Though it was intended as a bonding activity between the son and father based on pure scientific curiosity, this unintentionally fuelled Dahmer's fascination with death, anatomy and body control. Instead of fostering a healthy curiosity or respect for life, these experiences with roadkill seemed to

contribute to his later necrophilic tendencies. As an expression of his intense fear of rejection and loneliness, Dahmer began to view death as a means of maintaining companionship rather than as a natural end.

Despite numerous red flags throughout his adolescence, such as animal mutilation, alcohol misuse and social withdrawal, there were no effective measures or actions to address them. Although his peers and teachers noticed his troubled behaviour, it was so often overlooked or dismissed. His family, preoccupied with their own issues, failed to seek proper psychiatric evaluation or treatment for him. His conditions were allowed to worsen and fester due to a lack of professional psychological care during the crucial developmental period. His path might have been different if his symptoms had been identified and treated sooner. Dahmer's escalating substance abuse contributed to these mental and emotional problems. Alcohol became his primary coping mechanism, dulling his emotional pain, sexual confusion, and anxiety. Alcohol, however, lowered his inhibitions and weakened his already brittle judgement rather than dulling his urges. This toxic combination created a volatile state where he was able to act upon his most depraved fantasies without any regret or control. Ironically, his reliance on alcohol also created a vicious cycle where he drank to get away from his confusion and guilt, but drinking only intensified his compulsions.

"In this regard, for Dahmer, killing became 'a grotesque distortion of the act of love.... he had to kill in order to love, in order to indulge in the hideous parody of intimacy and cherishing which was the only kind of love he knew how to show'" (Derek Layder, sec.case study)

Dahmer's crimes also displayed clear sadistic and necrophilic elements. His desire to lobotomize victims to create a submissive, zombie-like partner manifested from a deep fear of abandonment and rejection, closely tied to his inner world. He sought to maintain absolute control over his victims by making them helpless and dependent on him. He believed that death

was the only way to gain control and permanence. This twisted need to control, paired with his inability to form emotional connections, shaped the horrific ritual that defined his crimes.

Jeffrey Dahmer's life and his crime highlight the tragic consequences of disregarding mental health issues. Even though his actions were unacceptable, it also revealed the critical need for early intervention and psychological care. Dahmer's story is not only about his horrific deed but also the missed opportunities to address his psychological issues. Early signs of distress, confusion about his sexual identity, and his fascination with corpses and roadkill were all clear indicators of untreated mental illness that might have altered his path from criminality if they had been identified early. His case underscores the importance of identifying and addressing mental health issues early on and fostering systemic awareness.

2. Socio-Psychological Analysis of Jeffrey Dahmer

The case of Jeffrey Dahmer presents an unsettling convergence of psychological disturbance and social failure. His horrific string of murders from 1978 to 1991 has continued to fascinate and horrify people due to the twisted nature of the crimes and circumstances that made them possible. The Netflix series *Monster: The Jeffrey Dahmer Story* (2022) offers a dramatized narrative that closely aligns with various academic perspectives. Drawing on socio-psychological frameworks such as social disorganization theory, strain theory, and labelling theory, this paper aims to examine the societal and structural factors that may have contributed to Dahmer's deviant behaviour.

According to Social Disorganization Theory, developed by Clifford Shaw and Henry McKay (1942), crime is more likely to occur in communities where social institutions such as family, school, and law enforcement are weaker. These areas often experience high levels of residential mobility, poverty, and ethnic heterogeneity, which are factors that limit social cohesion and informal social control.

Dahmer primarily operated in Milwaukee's inner-city neighbourhoods, particularly around his apartment at the Oxford Apartments. These areas were marked by economic decline, systemic neglect, and racial discrimination. The Netflix series highlights how this community instability contributes to Dahmer's criminality.

As previously demonstrated through the case of Glenda Cleveland, who persistently tried to alert law enforcement of Dahmer's suspicious behaviour, including disturbing noises and smells stemming from his apartment, her repeated warnings were continually dismissed by the police, particularly when the victims involved were men of colour or part of the LGBTQ+ community. This pattern of inaction indicates the deep-rooted institutional indifference and systemic biases, which enabled Dahmer to continue his crimes unchecked.

Furthermore, many of Dahmer's victims were marginalized individuals who were immigrants, racial minorities and members of the LGBTQ+ community who were socially or economically isolated. Their vulnerability made them easier targets for Dahmer to lure them without raising any immediate suspicion. In short, the social disorganization in the community not only created opportunities for crime but also made the victims invisible in the eyes of the system.

According to Robert K. Merton's Strain Theory, deviance arises when individuals are unable to achieve culturally approved goals through socially accepted means. This strain can result in deviant behaviour such as innovation, retreatism or rebellion. Dahmer's life reflected chronic emotional strain and disconnection. From an early age, he exhibited signs of emotional and psychological disturbance and struggled with the feeling of abandonment following his parent's turbulent relationship and eventual divorce. As he reached adolescence, he struggled to come to terms with his sexuality in a conservative American society where homosexuality was heavily stigmatized.

His inability to establish a deep, meaningful romantic relationship led to the development of disturbing fantasies that blurred the lines between affection and control. As depicted in the series *Monster*, his desire for emotional connection became entangled with his need for dominance. He seeks companionship through violent means such as drugging, drilling and performing makeshift lobotomies in an attempt to create obedient, zombie-like partners. These actions reflect Merton's concept of "innovation", where an individual uses illegitimate means to achieve culturally acceptable goals. In Dahmer's case, the goal was intimacy and companionship, but the approach to achieving his goal was disturbingly violent. His crimes were not simply the act of sadism but rather the product of unresolved emotional and social strain.

According to the Labelling theory by Howard Becker argues that once an individual is labelled as 'deviant' or 'other', they may start viewing themselves through that lens, which can result in a vicious cycle of marginalization and further deviance. It explores how individuals internalize societal labels and how these labels can lead to deviant behaviour.

From a young age, Dahmer was labelled as an "outcast". His teachers and peers noticed his strange behaviour, including fascination with animal corpses and a tendency to isolation, which solidified his reputation as a troubled misfit. Rather than receiving intervention or guidance, he was largely left alone to navigate his psychological confusion. As Dahmer became more alienated, he increasingly identified with his deviant behaviour. His repressed sexuality further intensified his isolation, pushing him into deviant action.

Moreover, the way society perceived both Dahmer and his victims shaped the outcome of key events. Based on the series, fourteen-year-old Konerak Sinthasomphone managed to escape from Dahmer's apartment. Despite being bruised and distressed, police officers accept Dahmer's explanation while ignoring the concerns of the bystander partly due to systemic biases against people of colour and the LGBTQ+ community. This tragic moment underscores

how systemic failure contributed to reinforcing these labels, further marginalizing the victims and enabling Dahmer's crimes. Understanding this theoretical framework is essential for both analyzing past crimes and preventing future ones. The factors that permitted Dahmer's crime may persist if systemic support remains inadequate, communities stay fragmented and deep-rooted bias goes unchallenged.

3. Conclusion

The Netflix series *Monster: The Jeffrey Dahmer Story* offers more than just a portrait of crime. It exposes how societal, institutional and personal failures can enable horrible crimes to continue unchecked. This research paper not only inspects Dahmer's actions but also the larger systemic pattern characterized by law enforcement negligence, overlooked mental health issues and deep-rooted societal and institutional biases. By doing this, the paper tries to highlight how crucial it is to approach serial crimes not only through a criminal perspective but also through a socio-psychological framework that accounts for the structural factors that enabled such violence to prevail.

Systemic failures were central to Dahmer's ability to carry out his crimes for over a decade. The tragic case of Konerak Sinthomsomphone underscores the dangerous impact of racial and sexual bias prevailing within the institution. Furthermore, it demonstrates how institutions often exclude the voices of marginalized people and communities. This pattern of negligence is an isolated incident, but they are the representation of a broader societal indifference toward the safety and dignity of minority populations.

Dahmer exhibited symptoms of multiple mental disorders, including borderline personality disorder (BPD), schizotypal personality disorder (SPD) and paraphilia. Instability, emotional neglect, and alienation shaped his troubled childhood, significantly contributing to his deteriorating mental health and his path to criminality. The failure of early psychological intervention highlights the urgent need for more extensive and accessible mental health

services, particularly for those who are showing early signs of emotional and psychological distress. This paper tries to underscore the link between mental health neglect and deviant behaviours, highlighting the necessity for preventive strategies rather than reactive measures.

Understanding Jeffrey Dahmer's actions requires a broader lens than one that simply focuses on the individual act. While mental disorders undoubtedly played a role, sociological perspectives demonstrate how systemic and societal factors contributed to his deviance. Social Disorder Theory shows why his acts went unnoticed for years due to systemic and societal failure. Strain theory offers insight into his emotional and psychological desolation, which led him to pursue his goals through violence and deviant behaviour. Labelling theory reveals how societal rejection and marginalization not only shaped Dahmer's identity but also made society and institutions ignorant of his victims.

Although *Monster: The Jeffrey Dahmer Story* has drawn criticism for potentially traumatising the families of the victims, the show plays a crucial role in shifting the narrative away from the glorification of the criminal to a critique of the systemic flaws and numerous missed opportunities that led him down to the path of criminality. The series explores the relevance of media ethics and criminal justice reform by highlighting systemic flaws and amplifying the voices of victims. By portraying this dimension, the series does not attempt to seek an excuse for Dahmer's actions; instead, it challenges the media's tendency to glorify serial killers and forces the audience to reconsider how such narratives can shape public perceptions of justice, morality and truth.

The case of Jeffrey Dahmer should not be written off as an isolated anomaly but rather as a sobering reflection of institutional and societal failures that allowed his crimes to continue unchecked. While his action was still inexcusable, they highlight the urgent need for systemic reform, beginning with confronting the racial and sexual biases embedded in law enforcement, ensuring comprehensive access to mental health care and reevaluating how society detects and

responds to early signs of emotional and psychological disturbance. Dahmer's story stands not only as a chilling warning of individual evil but as a damning indictment of the collective's indifference.

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